

Letter to the Editor

Effects of E-cigarettes on the Heart

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Received: February 4, 2020; **Accepted:** February 28, 2019; **Published:** May 17, 2020

Competing Interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Introduction

Electronic cigarettes are also known as e-cigarettes, e-vaporizers; these are battery operated devices that people use to inhale aerosol which includes nicotine (not always) with or without various flavors and other chemicals. [1]

Smoking damages roughly every organ in the body including heart. Almost one-third of deaths from heart disease are due to smoking and second hand smoke. Nicotine is a toxic chemical. It not only raises blood pressure and spikes your adrenaline but also increases heart rate and likelihood of having a heart attack. [2] In United States, smokers and second hand smokers causes approximately 34,000 early deaths from heart disease. Endothelial cells line the interior surface of blood vessels play vital role in heart and cardiovascular health. Although some studies suggested that e-cigarettes carry lower levels of carcinogens than traditional cigarettes – decreasing the risk of cancer. But the effect of e-cigarette use on vascular health has been uncertain. [3]

Fig. 1 Illustrates E-cigarettes can have a high-tech look [4]

E-cigarettes on heart may linked to coronary artery disease

Addictive nature of e-cigarettes used were estimated at 1 out of 20 Americans. As per scientist and according to data presented; new research shows that adults who report puffing e-cigarettes, vaping are significantly high and are more likely to have a heart attack, coronary artery disease and depression related with those who do not use them.

E-cigarettes are sometimes called as “vapes”, “e-cigs”, “vape pens” or “electronic nicotine delivery systems”. They work by heating e-liquid which contain combination of nicotine, solvent carriers and any number of flavors and other chemicals. According to research, they are more than 460 brands of e-cigarettes and over 7,700 flavors. Study found that compared with non-users, e-cigarette users were 56 percent more likely to have a heart attack and 30 percent more likely to suffer a stroke. Coronary artery disease and circulatory problems that includes blood clots. It was also noted that they suffer from depression, anxiety and other emotional problems. [5]

Fig. 2 Illustrates possible side effects of nicotine [4]

Heart attack risks are double for daily e-cigarette users

According to research e-cigarettes every day can almost double the odds of heart attack according to analysis of survey which was of almost 70,000 people; study led by researchers at UC San Francisco. Research also states that dual use of e-cigarettes and conventional cigarettes, the most common use pattern among e-cigarette users looks to be more dangerous than using either product alone. The research also found that risks compound that using daily use of both e-cigarettes and conventional cigarettes raises heart attack five-fold when differentiated to the people who don't use either product.

In this study it was examined the relationship between e-cigarette use and heart attacks and to understand the effects of e-cigarettes on long term health. Although, e-cigarettes deliver lower levels of carcinogens than

conventional cigarettes, they deliver both ultrafine particles which are around 1/50 to 1/100 the size of a human hair and other toxins that are linked to increased cardiovascular and non-cancer lung disease risks. [6, 7]

One e-cigarette with nicotine may lead to adrenaline changes

A new research and study at University of California Los Angeles (UCLA) demonstrated that healthy non-smokers had increased adrenaline levels in their heart after one e-cigarette with nicotine but there were no increased adrenaline levels when the research subjects used a nicotine-free or empty e-cigarette.

Unlike traditional cigarettes, e-cigarettes have no combustion or tobacco. Instead these electronic handheld devices carries nicotine with flavoring and other chemicals in a vapor instead of smoke. Scientists previously reported that chronic e-cigarettes users have elevated sympathetic nerve activity which increases adrenaline that is directed to the heart and more affected to oxidative stress. Both are risk for heart attack. Research team members used a technique called “heart rate variability” obtained from a prolonged, non-invasive heart rhythm recording. Heart rate variability is calculated from the degree of variability in the time between heartbeats. This variability may indicate the amount of adrenaline on the heart. [8, 9]

Fig. 3 Illustrates Percent of Youths who reported recent vaping [10]

E-cigarette flavorings may damage blood vessels

As per study flavors additives that used in electronic cigarettes and related tobacco products could diminish blood vessel function and may be an early indication of heart damage.

Nine chemical flavors such as menthol (mint), vanillin (vanilla), cinnamaldehyde (cinnamon), diacetyl (butter), isoamyl acetate (banana), eugenol (clove), dimethylpyrazine (strawberry), acetylpyridine (burnt flavor) and eucalyptol (spicy cooling) which are used widely used in e-cigarettes, e-hookah, little cigars and cigarillos were tested for their short term effects on endothelial cells, the cells which line blood vessels and are inside of the heart. Experts found that all nine flavors are dangerous to cells in laboratory at the highest levels and all the flavors impaired nitric oxide production in endothelial cells in culture. Other additives such as clove, cinnamon, vanilla, menthol and burnt flavoring resulted in higher inflammatory marker and lower levels of nitric oxide; a molecule that inhibits inflammation, clotting and controls vessels ability to widen in response to greater blood flow. [11, 12]

As per study electronic cigarettes are harmful

As per study by researchers 23 addicted e-cigarette users (used most days for at least one year) and 19 non-users between ages of 21 and 45 years. It was found that addicted e-cigarette users were more likely than non-users to have higher cardiac sympathetic activity (increased adrenaline levels in the heart)

As per researchers findings e-cigarettes have critical implications for the long term cardiac risks associated with addiction and mandate re-examination of aerosolized nicotine and its metabolites. They also added additional information that root cause cannot be confirmed on basis of single, small study and there is need further research into potential adverse cardiovascular health effects of e-cigarettes is warranted. [13, 14]

Fig. 4 Illustrates more high school students use e-cigarettes than regular cigarettes. The use of e-cigarettes is higher among high school students than adults [4]

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest as per Author's point of view.

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